

Project DEFINERS – Interview Protocol

Title: Exploring Teachers’ Technology-Mediated Language Teaching and Learning

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Interview Protocol

1. Purpose and scope

This semi-structured interview protocol explores how language teachers use digital technologies and resources for teaching and learning languages. It is adapted from Shafiee et al. (2022) and aligns with the objectives of Project DEFINERS to document educators' digital practices and professional identities.

2. Ethical and practical notes for interviewers

- Obtain informed consent and remind participants of their right to withdraw at any time.
- Use the demographic questions to create a comfortable starting point.
- Follow the question order but probe organically for depth and examples.
- Estimated duration: 45–60 minutes.
- Record audio (and video if permitted) for transcription.

3. Demographic information

Use open text unless otherwise noted.

1. Sex/gender
2. Age
3. Previous education and academic level
4. Place of birth / current residence
5. Period(s) of residence abroad (> 3 months)
6. L1(s)
7. Other languages you are learning + proficiency level
8. Hours per day using other languages for non-academic activities (specify activities)
9. Language(s) with most formal study (with a teacher)
10. Language(s) with most self-directed study
11. Language(s) used most for leisure
12. Language(s) you teach or aim to teach
13. Total time & experience teaching these languages

4. Core interview questions

Note on semi-structured nature of the interview. This is a semi-structured interview: use the italicized sub-prompts to dig into the why and how behind each answer, while staying open to unexpected yet meaningful topics. If something is unclear to the interviewee, reword the question for clarity instead of repeating it. When new insights emerge beyond the scripted questions, explore them fully before gently steering the conversation back to the protocol.

1. **Defining digital resources.** From your perspective, what counts as a *digital technology or resource*? Elicit multiple examples if possible.
2. **Technology for formal language learning (as learner).** What digital resources do you use in academic contexts to learn languages? How do you use them and how often? *Follow-up:* Outside class, are you using them primarily to *learn* languages or for other goals that incidentally foster language learning? Advantages/limitations? Evidence of skill gains?
3. **Technology for teaching.** What digital resources do you employ when teaching languages? How? How frequently?
4. **Skill-specific support.** Do technologies enhance certain language skills more than others? Which and why? Recent example of advantages or limitations?
5. **Recent classroom episode.** Describe a recent lesson where you integrated technology. Which tools? How did you familiarize yourself with them? Impact on teaching and student learning?
6. **Extending learning beyond the classroom.** Do you (or would you) require students to use digital resources outside class? If so, how do/would you teach them to do so effectively? Provide an example.
7. **Linguistic diversity.** Do digital tools foster or hinder inclusion of linguistic diversity? Illustrate with a recent example—or explain why you refrained.
8. **Teacher confidence and professional growth.** How confident are you using technology for teaching? How do you keep your skills updated?
 - On your own
 - Online tutorials
 - Colleagues at work/study
 - Online professional communities
 - Formal PD courses.

Prompt: Recall a recent challenge and how you addressed it.

9. **Comparing technology-mediated vs. non-technology lessons.** What are the main differences? How do they affect student learning and teacher roles?
10. **Ideal language teacher.** Describe key qualities. How have recent technological advances reshaped teachers' roles/responsibilities? Should the ideal teacher master digital tools?
If AI not mentioned: Are you familiar with recent AI developments and their implications for language education?
11. **Ethical considerations.** What moral dilemmas arise when using technology for language teaching/learning? Example and mitigation strategy?
12. **Limitations and challenges.** What personal, contextual, or administrative barriers do you face in using technology? How do you overcome them?
13. **Promoting out-of-class interaction.** Do you encourage students to use technology to communicate in the target language beyond class? How?
14. **Social networking sites and video games.** Do you view social networking sites and/or video games as useful for language teaching/learning—inside or outside class? Explain.
15. **Artificial intelligence (if not yet covered).** How do you see AI influencing language teaching and learning? How is AI influencing your own teaching or learning?